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Usage of songs in teaching English as a second language

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Abstract: The Effect of Using Songs on Young Learners and Their Motivation for Learning English.

Аннотация: влияние использования песен на юных учащихся и их мотивацию к изучению английского языка.

Key words: listening activity, songs, young learners, motivation to learn, help learners.

Ключевые слова: слушание, песни, младшие школьники, мотивация к обучению, помощь учащимся.

The primary aim of this study was to explore the views of Turkish state primary school EFL teachers about songs and using songs in teaching English to young learners. English language teachers' opinions were collected through a questionnaire and the results demonstrated that Turkish EFL teachers have strong beliefs about the pedagogical value of songs and about the effectiveness of using songs in teaching EFL to young learners. However, findings showed that teachers had difficulty in accessing to appropriate songs to use in their classes and in measuring student success when they use songs. Therefore, it was suggested in this study that teachers be provided with song materials to use in their classes. Measuring student success was closely related to how to teach songs, and therefore

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it was suggested that teachers be given in-service training about how to teach songs. To conclude, we may argue that the findings of this study strengthened previous research findings about the role of songs in teaching English to young learners.

When using songs, it is of immense importance not to teach the target language structures but to let children learn and discover the language on their own. In this process they need to get the feeling of success.

The language needs to be presented at an attainable rate as well as to connect previous words and language structures to the ones that will be learned in the near future. The questioning cycle explains how learners process the new language in a song. They first recognize the new language forms, and then they want to learn them because they need them for the activity they like. So, they try to understand the words by finding out their meanings. After that, they use this new language and connect it with other words from the song. In this way learners develop positive attitude and willingness to learn.

Every teacher may have his/her own way of using songs in his/her lessons. Regardless of the way it is taught, the key to successful use of a song is its application. That is to say that the presentation and activities have to suit young learners' characteristics, their mastery of the language and their interests. In order to accomplish this, a certain technique has to be applied. The suggested, but

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flexible, procedure is as the context.

Use visual aids to introduce new vocabulary.

Play or sing the song to familiarize students with it.

Do further listening activity.

Practice pronunciation

Encourage students to join in and do actions or mime. Repeat the song several times.

Give students written text of the song. The text can further be used for multiple activities, such as: gap-fill, listen and sequence, illustrate, match pictures with line, etc.

Invite students to compare the song with a similar one in their own language.

References

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